

Ti and TiAlV foils enhanced with PLD and flash-deposited carbon: On cytocompatibility and antibacterial activity

Petr Slepíčka^{a,*}, Klaudia Hurtuková^a, Silvie Rimpelová^b, Šárka Trhoňová^a, Jiří Martan^c, Michal Procházka^c, Václav Švorčík^a, Nikola Slepíčková Kasálková^a

^a Department of Solid State Engineering, The University of Chemistry and Technology Prague, 166 28 Prague, Czech Republic

^b Department of Biochemistry and Microbiology, University of Chemistry and Technology Prague, 166 28 Prague, Czech Republic

^c New Technologies - Research Centre, University of West Bohemia, Univerzitní 8, 301 00 Plzeň, Czech Republic

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Titanium
TiAlV
Surface enhancement
Surface nanopattern
Morphology
Excimer laser
Carbon
Tissue engineering

ABSTRACT

In this study, we investigated the effects of carbon layer deposition on titanium (Ti) and titanium alloy (TiAlV) substrates using "flash" vaporization and pulsed laser deposition (PLD) techniques. Raman spectroscopy revealed that the PLD method produced a higher sp³ carbon bond content than the evaporation method (61 vs. 47 %). Atomic force microscopy and surface wettability analyzes showed differences in surface roughness and contact angle, with PLD-deposited samples exhibiting enhanced hydrophilicity and wrinkled morphology. Subsequent laser annealing optimized surface properties by increasing hydrophobicity, which is critical for cell adhesion. Surface chemistry analysis via scanning electron microscopy and energy dispersive spectroscopy demonstrated significant carbon enrichment in the PLD-deposited samples, mainly for TiAlV substrate. Cytocompatibility tests using human osteosarcoma cells (U-2 OS) revealed varying cell adhesion and proliferation based on surface modification, with PLD-deposited layers promoting better cell interaction. Both carbon deposition techniques enhanced antibacterial effect. This suggests the potential of PLD-deposited carbon layers for biomedical applications, particularly in enhancing implant surfaces for improved cell growth and adhesion, and reduce bacteria, the nanostructured substrates may serve also for subsequent replication process into polymer.

Introduction

Carbon layers ranging from amorphous carbon (a-C) to diamond or diamond-like structure, can be synthesized using a variety of techniques (Ohtake et al., 2021; Robertson, 2002; Bewilogua and Hofmann, 2014). Key methods include chemical vapor deposition (CVD) (Gangopadhyay, 1998), physical vapor deposition (PVD), and pulsed laser deposition (PLD) (Hu et al., 2007; Lin et al., 2017). PVD includes techniques based on evaporation and sputtering (Honglertkongsakul et al., 2010). Carbon layers produced by these methods exhibit exceptional properties including high hardness, unique chemical structures, and tunable optical band gaps, all of which depend on the deposition conditions. The structure and properties of carbon layers formed by various deposition techniques have been widely studied through both experimental and theoretical approaches (Bewilogua and Hofmann, 2014; Erdemir and Donnet, 2006). Among the lesser-known yet highly effective methods of vapor deposition is "flash" vaporization, noted for its distinct characteristics (Švorčík et al., 2009).

Amorphous carbon (a-C) layers are particularly valued for their versatility and precise control over a wide range of properties. These layers can be tailored to exhibit a spectrum of mechanical, electrical, and optical properties ranging from soft to hard, conductive to insulating, and transparent to opaque. In the automotive industry, a-C layers are highly valued for their excellent friction resistance, which enhances the durability of moving parts, reduces maintenance needs, and improves vehicle efficiency (Iwamura, 2013). Hydrogen-enriched layers (a-C:H), due to their low production costs, ability to be fabricated at room temperature, high mechanical flexibility, and strong adhesion to substrates like glass, plastics, silicon wafers, and metals are ideal for electronic applications (Bi et al., 2017). Amorphous carbon layers, particularly diamond-like carbon (DLC) films, are extensively utilized in the aerospace industry for their lightweight nature and superior wear and corrosion resistance, crucial for components operating in extreme conditions (Alotaibi and Manjunatha, 2018). These layers are also valuable for optical components such as lenses and mirrors, due to protection against scratches and contamination (Voevodin et al., 1999;

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: petr.slepicka@vscht.cz (P. Slepíčka).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jajp.2024.100274>

Rajak et al., 2021). In the energy sector, especially in applications involving turbine blades and solar panels, carbon coatings enhance efficiency and durability under harsh environmental and operational conditions (Vetter, 2014). To improve mechanical properties such as hardness and wear resistance, carbon layers are often doped with elements such as silicon, titanium, chromium, and tungsten. Doping with elements such as germanium, nitrogen, and platinum enhances the electrical and electronic properties of the coatings, thus modulating conductivity, and semiconductor characteristics, which are important for various electronic and optoelectronic applications (Doll, 2022; Kattamis et al., 1996; Ren et al., 2019). Iodine is particularly effective in improving optical properties and increasing chemical reactivity, while fluorine is known for reducing friction and increasing wear resistance (Ray et al., 2016; Zia, 2020; Sasamoto et al., 2021; Sharifahmadian et al., 2023).

Titanium and its alloys play a crucial role in modern technology and industry due to their unique combination of physical and mechanical properties. With a low density, high strength-to-weight ratio, excellent biocompatibility, corrosion resistance, favorable plasticity, and mechanical properties, titanium is widely used across various sectors, including aerospace, automotive, energy and shipbuilding, architecture, medicine, and sports equipment (Dorner et al., 2001; Viteri and Fuentes, 2013). The medical use of commercially pure titanium (CP-Ti) dates back to the 1940s when its exceptional bone compatibility was first demonstrated. This discovery and advancements in manufacturing techniques spurred significant interest in titanium for medical applications (Sarraf et al., 2021). Today, commercially pure titanium and its alloys are considered the gold standard for bone biomaterials due to their favorable mechanical properties and biocompatibility. Key attributes include high specific strength, fracture toughness, and a low modulus of elasticity, which minimizes stress shielding in the surrounding bone, reducing the risk of bone resorption. Additionally, the rapid formation of a passive, stable oxide layer on titanium surfaces provides high corrosion resistance and contributes to its biocompatibility (Mutreja et al., 2020; Dwivedi et al., 2011; Jackson et al., 2016).

Among the various titanium grades, commercially pure titanium (CP-Ti, grade 2) and its alloy Ti-6Al-4V (grade 5) are the most commonly used in biomedical applications. CP-Ti is primarily used for dental implants, while the Ti-6Al-4V is preferred in applications requiring higher strength, such as artificial hip and knee joints. Ongoing research aims to develop new titanium alloys to address current challenges, including the release of toxic ions and mechanical property mismatches. Alloying elements such as niobium, zirconium, molybdenum, tin, and tantalum are being explored for their potential to reduce titanium modulus of elasticity, thereby improving its suitability for biomedical applications (Jackson et al., 2016; Jongwannasiri et al., 2023; Karkalos et al., 2023). Titanium and its alloys thus play an integral role in both industrial and medical fields, offering innovative solutions to a wide range of challenges. In particular, the application of DLC coatings on implant surfaces has emerged as an effective strategy to improve hemocompatibility. DLC coating effectively limits the activation of the coagulation cascade, reduces platelet adhesion, and mitigates inflammatory response, significantly lowering the risk of implant wear, corrosion, and tissue damage. This, in turn, enhances the functionality of implants and minimizes the formation of debris in the surrounding tissues (Jongwannasiri et al., 2023).

A study (Zia et al., 2023) demonstrated that metal implants coated with DLC showed a 100 % decrease in wear rate compared to metal/metal and metal/polyethylene composites. In particular, for hip joints, applying DLC coatings to the metal femoral head resulted in a tenfold decrease in the wear of the plastic acetabular cup. However, DLC layers face challenges such as delamination and peeling due to high internal residual stresses. These issues limit their use, especially in applications involving high contact voltages, and restrict the maximum thickness of the deposited layers. Recently, several strategies have been developed to improve DLC film properties, including using interlayers (e.g., titanium,

silicon nitride, chromium carbide) and incorporating additional elements (Zhang et al., 2020; Caschera et al., 2011; Buchegger et al., 2017). Adding various metals to the DLC matrix significantly enhances wear resistance, thermal stability, toughness, and adhesion leading to the development of metal-DLC films (Caschera et al., 2011).

Bacterial infections related to implants represent a serious concern in orthopedic surgery, posing a significant health risk and economic burden (Harrasser et al., 2016). These infections arise when bacteria colonize the surfaces of biomaterials, leading to life-threatening complications and postoperative issues, often requiring reoperations extended hospitalizations, and patient recovery time (Bociaga et al., 2015). DLC coatings on implants offer a promising solution by improving hemocompatibility and reducing coagulation and inflammatory responses. Marciano and colleagues (Marciano et al., 2009, 2011) reported the antibacterial effects of DLC films applied to stainless steel substrates with a silicone interlayer. The films have tested against Gram-positive (G+; *Staphylococcus aureus*) and Gram-negative (G-; *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Salmonella typhimurium*) bacteria. Their results showed that DLC films were particularly effective against two G- strains of *E. coli* and *S. typhimurium* when tested in direct contact with the surface. Additionally, the films with low hydrogen content and hydrophobic properties exhibited increased bactericidal activity.

Since 2011, it has been recognized that materials coated with DLC films have significant antibacterial properties and a low risk of antimicrobial resistance. The antimicrobial effects of DLC are attributed to a combination of different physical and chemical mechanisms, including disruption of the peptidoglycan cell wall, microbial entrapment, electron transfer, and the induction of oxidative stress through reactive oxygen species. These mechanisms provide DLC coatings with broad-spectrum antimicrobial and antibiofilm capabilities, making them promising for long-term use in advanced medical implants (Birkett et al., 2023). Carbon coatings, whether in the form of nanoparticles, thin films, or heat-treated modifications, have found widespread applications in both tissue engineering and antibacterial technologies (Grausova, 2009; Švorčík et al., 2024; Slepicka et al., 2015; Slepickáová Kasálková et al., 2015; Žáková et al., 2016; Žáková et al., 2017; Neděla et al., 2017; Slepicka, 2018; Kopova et al., 2018; Slepicka et al., 2018; Lišková et al., 2019).

The successful development of metal-DLC films is critical for their use in medicinal applications. Controlled incorporation of metal ions into DLC layers stabilizes the metal particles within the matrix, preventing agglomeration (Marciano et al., 2009). Various deposition techniques, including CVD with plasma enhancement, PLD, and sputtering, have been employed to create these films (Paul et al., 2009; Wang et al., 2021; Orrit-Prat et al., 2021; Jastrzębski et al., 2021; Jing et al., 2021). In the case of Ag-DLC films, the antibacterial effect primarily depends on silver ions released from the film. Interestingly, the antibacterial properties of the films are not linearly dependent on the silver concentration, suggesting that increasing the silver content does not always result in improved antibacterial performance. While many studies indicate that higher concentrations of silver enhance the antibacterial properties of Ag-DLC films, others suggest that the effect may not always be consistent (Țălu et al., 2020).

The development of antimicrobial surfaces has gained increasing attention as a potential solution to the growing issue of antibiotic resistance. Recent research has focused on an alternative method to prevent bacterial adhesion by developing micro and nano-textured surfaces inspired by natural antibacterial and anti-biofouling properties. These surfaces represent a promising strategy for the passive control of bacterial infections in biomedical applications. Integrating carbon coatings with Ti and TiAlV surfaces has emerged as an effective approach for surface modification, providing synergistic effects and improved antibacterial performance. Using high-energy excimer lasers for pulsed laser deposition, post-treatment, and vacuum evaporation has led to the formation of surfaces with strong antibacterial properties,

which are also conducive to the growth of U2-OS cells.

Experimental details

Materials

Titanium foil of 100- μm thickness and purity $\geq 99.600\%$ (Goodfellow Ltd., Huntingdon, UK) and titanium alloy foil ($\text{Ti}_{90}\text{Al}_6\text{V}_4$) of 75- μm thickness and grade 5 (Goodfellow Ltd., Huntingdon, UK) were used in this study. For direct pulsed laser deposition, carbon foil of 75- μm thickness and 99.800% purity, and flexible graphite (Goodfellow Ltd., Huntingdon, UK) were used.

Excimer laser treatment

A laser beam was applied for two distinct techniques: PLD and pulsed laser annealing. In both cases, a high-power excimer KrF laser (Coherent Inc., Santa Clara, California, USA, Leap 100K) was used at a wavelength of 248 nm, a pulse duration of 20–40 ns, an output energy of up to 1000 mJ cm^{-2} , and beam size of $32 \times 13 \text{ mm}^2$. In all cases, the laser beam acted parallelly to the normal of the sample surface (at the angle of 0°).

PLD was used to create a continuous carbon layer (close to the DLC layer) on the surface of titanium and titanium alloy foils. The PLD process occurred in a vacuum chamber at a pressure of $4.6 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ Pa}$ and a carbon foil was used as a target (see Fig. 1). To achieve a carbon layer with the highest possible content of *sp*³ carbon hybridization, the beam energy impacting the target's surface was higher than maximum energy of the device output beam. The higher energy was achieved by focusing the output beam through a lens. In the case of depositing a carbon layer on the surface of titanium foil and titanium alloy foil, the laser energy value was set to 2000 mJ cm^{-2} at 5 Hz and 120 pulses. The lens was at a distance of 23 cm from the vacuum chamber, which made it possible to reach the size of the irradiated surface at 15 mm^2 . The energy, frequency, and number of pulses of the laser beam affected the height of the deposited layer. In the case of using lower energy (2000 mJ cm^{-2}), the thickness of the carbon layer was $100 \pm 4 \text{ nm}$. Pulsed laser annealing (PLA) with KrF beams took place in a vacuum environment or ambient atmosphere, the energy of the laser beam was 150 mJ cm^{-2} . A single shot of the laser beam was applied.

Carbon evaporation by flash technique

Carbon layers on the surface of titanium foil and titanium alloy foil were deposited using the SDC 050 BAL-TEC device by the flash evaporation process using a double carbon fiber. The device consists of a sliding table, which can be moved vertically in the range of 3 to 7 cm concerning the carbon fiber stretched on the steam head, which makes it possible to apply a carbon layer of different thicknesses. The process takes place in a vacuum environment. First, the fiber is degassed (the so-called removal of impurities and gaseous admixtures), which is achieved

by heating it using a current of 1.5 A. After the fiber is degassed, it is evaporated with a current of $\approx 13 \text{ A}$. To achieve different thicknesses of the carbon layer, the substrate was placed on the table at a distance of 7, 5, or 3 cm from the source carbon fiber.

Descriptions of experimental evaluations

Atomic force microscopy

Surface morphology and roughness of the pristine and treated films were examined by atomic force microscopy (AFM) using Dimension ICON (Bruker Corp., Billerica, MA, USA). The samples were analyzed in Scan-Assyst® mode using nitride lever SCANASYST-AIR with Si tip (spring constant of 0.4 N m^{-1}). NanoScope Analysis software was applied for data processing. Surface roughness (R_a) represents the arithmetic mean of the absolute values of the height deviations measured from the central plane.

Scanning electron microscopy

The morphology of the sample surfaces was also characterized by scanning electron microscope FIB-SEM LYRA3 GMU (Tescan, Brno, Czech Republic). The acceleration voltage was set to 10 kV.

The elemental composition was measured by energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS, analyzer X-ManN, 20 mm^2 SDD detector, Oxford Instruments, United Kingdom), while the accelerating voltage for SEM-EDS analysis was set to 10 kV.

Raman spectroscopy

Raman analysis was performed using a DXR microscope dispersive Raman spectrometer from Thermo Scientific (Waltham, Massachusetts, USA). The system was equipped with an Olympus confocal microscope and a thermoelectrically cooled CCD detector. A solid-state Nd:YAG laser with a wavelength of 532 nm and a maximum power of 10 mW was used as an excitation source. A 900 lines/mm grating, 25 μm slit aperture, and 50 \times magnification objective were used. The measurement conditions included a laser power of 10 mW, an acquisition time of 10 s per scan, and 20 repetitions. Ten spectra were averaged from each surface. The obtained data were processed using Omnic 9 software (Thermo Scientific, Waltham, Massachusetts, USA). The recorded Raman spectra were fitted using Origin software, using a Voigt profile that combines Gaussian and Lorentzian profiles.

Wettability

The wettability of the studied samples was determined by measurement of contact angles (CA, θ) using goniometer Advex Instruments (Brno, Czech Republic) connected to the SEE System 7.1 program. Analysis of CA was performed at room temperature with 8 μL drops of distilled water (dyed with methyl violet) using a Transferpette® automatic pipette (Brand, Wertheim, Germany) at 6 different positions of 3 samples in parallel and perpendicular directions. Subsequently, the drops were photographed and evaluated by 3 marked points.

Fig. 1. Scheme of pulse laser deposition process.

Antibacterial activity

The antibacterial effects of samples with titanium foil and titanium alloy foil together with deposited carbon layers were measured by the drop method using two bacterial strains of Gram-positive (G+) *Staphylococcus aureus* (CCM4516) and Gram-negative (G-) *E. coli* (CCM4517). First, bacterial inocula were prepared from one colony of each bacterial strain in Luria-Bertani medium (LB, Sigma-Aldrich) and incubated overnight shaking at 37 °C. The next day, the inocula were diluted into phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) solution to 5×10^3 and 2.5×10^3 per ml of *S. aureus* and *E. coli*, respectively. Then, 100 μ l of the bacterial suspension was dropped onto the surface of the samples. After 2 and 24 h, three drops (25 μ l) from each drop were placed on agar culture dishes (PCA, Oxoid, 17.5 g.l⁻¹). The agar plates were incubated at 37 °C overnight, after which the number of CFU was determined. As a control, bacteria incubated in PBS were used. The experiment was performed under sterile conditions.

Cytocompatibility evaluation

For cytocompatibility evaluation of the Ti and Ti alloy foils, human cells from osteosarcoma (U-2 OS) were used. The cells were supplied from the American Tissue Culture Collection (Manassas, Virginia, USA) and cultivated in high-glucose Dulbecco's modified Eagle's medium (DMEM; Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, Missouri, USA) with stable L-glutamine and 10 % fetal bovine serum (FBS; Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, Massachusetts, USA). The cells were regularly passaged, kept at the exponential phase of growth, and incubated at 37 °C, 95 % humidity, and in a 5 % CO₂ atmosphere.

First, the Ti and Ti alloy foils were sterilized using 70 % (v/v) ethanol in water for 30 min. Then, they were placed into wells of 12-well cell culture plates (ϕ 2.14 cm; VWR, Radnor, PA, USA), washed with sterile PBS, and weighed by hollow polymethyl methacrylate cylinders (Zenit, Prague, Czech Republic). After that, the samples were inoculated with U-2 OS cells (1.5×10^4 cells per 1 cm²) in 1 ml of DMEM; in triplicate. As a control, tissue culture polystyrene was used. After 24, 48, and 72 h of incubation, the cells were fixed using 4 % formaldehyde solution in PBS for 20 min. at room temperature in the dark. Then, the fixative was discarded, the cells were washed twice with PBS and stained with 0.5 μ g.ml⁻¹ of 4',6-diamidino-2-phenylindole (DAPI; Sigma-Aldrich, USA) and 2 μ g.ml⁻¹ of phalloidin-Atto565 (AttoTec, Germany) in PBS for 15 min. Then, the cells were washed twice with PBS and kept in the dark at 4 °C.

Fluorescence microscopy

Fluorescence microscopic analysis of U-2 OS cells cultured on the examined substrates was performed using an inverted fluorescence microscope (Olympus IX-81, Japan) with xCellence software. The stained cells were captured using 10, 20, and 40 \times objectives with NA 0.30, 0.45, and 0.60, respectively. The F-actin and cell nuclei were monitored using a DAPI/FITC/TRITC triple filter cube (Olympus, Japan). At least 10 fields of view were captured from each sample. Then, the fluorescent images were background-corrected and the fluorescent channels were merged. The number of cells per 1 cm² was evaluated using Image J 1.53 software. The data from individual fields of view and replicates were averaged and the standard deviation was calculated.

Results and discussion

Raman spectroscopy

The sp³ composition of the carbon layer deposited on the substrates by pulsed laser deposition was investigated using Raman spectroscopy. Fig. 2 presents the Raman spectrum of a sample with a carbon layer deposited by the PLD method (CPLD). The Raman spectrum of amorphous carbon typically exhibits two broad peaks: the D band, located between 1200 – 1450 cm⁻¹, and the G band, found between 1500 – 1700

Fig. 2. Raman spectroscopy plot of a CPLD-coated glass slide sample. The graph shows the proportion of sp³ bonds in the glass/CPLD sample.

cm⁻¹.

In the Raman analysis of the glass/CPLD sample shown in Fig. 2, the exact positions and intensities of the D and G peaks were identified, enabling a detailed calculation of the ratio between sp³ and sp² hybridized carbon bonds. The D peak was observed at 1367 cm⁻¹, while the G peak appeared at 1546 cm⁻¹. From the intensity and position of these peaks, the sp³/sp² bond ratio was determined, revealing that 61 % were sp³ bonds and the rest were sp² bonds.

The high proportion of sp³ hybridization layers led to an increased presence of the combination of amorphous carbon layer (a-C) with DLC layer compared to the vaporized carbon layer C3, which exhibited only 47 % sp³ bonds. DLC layers are well known for their wide application in the medical field, owing to their exceptional ability to support cell adhesion and proliferation.

Atomic force microscopy

The surface morphology changes of Ti and TiAlV foils, before and after the application of carbon layers, were analyzed and compared using AFM. Fig. 3 shows AFM images of Ti and TiAlV foils, both in their untreated stage and following carbon layer deposition by two different methods: "flash" evaporation (C3) and pulsed laser deposition (CPLD).

Fig. 3 highlights the differences in morphology and surface roughness between pristine and treated Ti and TiAlV foils. The surface of the untreated Ti foil exhibits distinct, narrow depressions that run along its length, accompanied by unevenly distributed nanometric to micrometric needle-like structures. These features contribute to a surface roughness of 50.1 nm with an effective surface area of 4.6 %. In contrast, the surface of the TiAlV foil presents a wrinkled morphology with a roughness of 18.4 nm and an effective area of 0.5 %. On the Ti foil, the height variation of the "scratches" reached up to 500 nm, indicating deeper and more pronounced surface structures. In comparison, the wrinkles on the TiAlV foil surface reached a height of only 150 nm. Thus, the Ti foil demonstrates a more organized surface topology with larger height variations, whereas the TiAlV foil shows a more irregular surface with smaller height differences.

After the deposition of carbon layers, both surface roughness and morphology showed slight changes. For the Ti/C3 sample, the roughness decreased from 50.1 to 44.5 nm, while the effective surface area increased to 5.6 % compared to the untreated Ti sample. The surface morphology of the Ti/C3 sample remained similar to that of the original Ti foil, though it appeared rougher with more pronounced needle-like structures, likely due to the carbon layer. The height of the "scratches" reduced to a 400 nm, which can be attributed to the filling of these

Fig. 3. AFM images of titanium (Ti) and titanium alloy (TiAlV) foils before and after carbon layer deposition by two different methods: "flash" evaporation (C3) and pulsed laser deposition (CPLD). The scanned area was $10 \times 10 \mu\text{m}^2$. R_a - arithmetic average of surface roughness; S - an effective surface area with a difference from the base area in %.

features by the carbon layer. The Ti/CPLD sample exhibited a similar surface morphology but with slight wrinkling compared to the Ti/C3 sample. The surface roughness measured 45.0 nm, and the effective area was 4.3 % with the "scratch" height remaining at 400 nm. For the TiAlV/C3 sample, surface roughness increased slightly from 18.4 to 20.5 nm, while the effective area decreased to 0.3 %. The surface morphology displayed less pronounced wrinkling compared to the untreated TiAlV foil, with needle-like structures similar to those observed on the Ti/C3 sample. In contrast, the TiAlV/CPLD sample had the most pronounced wrinkling and the highest number of needle-like structures among all TiAlV and TiAlV/C3 samples. The roughness of the TiAlV/CPLD sample reached 18.7 nm, with an effective area of 1.8 %, attributed to the wrinkled surface morphology. The wrinkle height across all TiAlV samples remained consistent at 150 nm.

Surface wettability

Surface roughness and wettability play a crucial role in the interaction between cells and materials, particularly affecting their ability to adhere (Majhy et al., 2021). Most cells exhibit optimal adhesion and growth on surfaces with moderate hydrophilicity, typically at contact angles between 40° and 70° . In contrast, surfaces that are too hydrophilic

(contact angle $<5^\circ$) or superhydrophobic (contact angle greater than 150°) tend to be less favorable for cell adhesion. Hydrophilic surfaces can promote cell differentiation, while superhydrophobic surfaces can alter the conformation of fibronectin, thereby impairing cell attachment (Slepicka et al., 2012; Al-Azzam and Alazzam, 2022).

A contact angle study was conducted on Ti foil with deposited carbon layers to assess wettability. Fig. 4 presents a value of contact angle for samples of Ti foil and that with a carbon layer deposited by "flash" evaporation (Ti/C3) and pulsed laser deposition (Ti/CPLD), measured 1 h after deposition. The graph also includes images from the contact angle measurements for each sample.

Fig. 4 clearly shows that the titanium foil (Ti) exhibited the highest contact angle, measuring $96.3 \pm 0.5^\circ$. Following the deposition of carbon layers, there was a significant reduction in the contact angle, indicating increased surface wettability. The Ti/C3 sample displayed a contact angle of $58.6 \pm 2.3^\circ$, while the Ti/CPLD sample had the lowest contact angle at $25.3 \pm 4.5^\circ$. This decrease in contact angle can be attributed to the deposited carbon and the possible oxidation of the CPLD layers' surface upon exposure to air after removal from the vacuum chamber, potentially leading to surface hydrophilization.

Considering that the contact angle for the Ti/CPLD sample falls outside the optimal range for cell adhesion and proliferation, further

Fig. 4. The water contact angle on the titanium foil (Ti) surface and titanium foil with a carbon layer deposited by "flash" evaporation (Ti/C3) and pulsed laser deposition (Ti/C_{PLD}) methods.

surface modifications were undertaken to increase the contact angle without significantly altering surface morphology. It was observed that exposure to a single laser beam pulse increased the contact angle, likely due to the slight ablation of the oxidized surface layer, which forms after the sample is exposed to air. Therefore, this method was applied to optimize the surface properties and to reduce surface wettability, aiming to improve conditions for cell adhesion.

The surface of the Ti/C_{PLD} samples was subsequently modified using a single pulse of a laser beam (L) with sufficiently low energy to avoid altering the surface morphology while enhancing hydrophobicity. The morphological changes were analyzed using AFM. The laser fluence was set at 150 mJ cm^{-2} and applied in both ambient and vacuum environments.

Fig. 5 illustrates the contact angle measurements on titanium foil with a carbon layer deposited by the PLD method, followed by laser annealing (L) at the energy of 150 mJ cm^{-2} in the ambient atmosphere (Ti/C_{PLD}/Latm.) and vacuum (Ti/C_{PLD}/Lvac). The contact angles were measured 1 h after the last modification.

As shown in the graph, exposure to the laser beam in the ambient atmosphere resulted in only a slight increase in the contact angle to $29.0 \pm 3.6^\circ$, which was almost identical to the original value of the Ti/C_{PLD} sample. In contrast, a significant change occurred when the laser was applied in a vacuum, with the contact angle increasing to $54.4 \pm 2.4^\circ$, indicating a substantial improvement in surface hydrophobicity.

Furthermore, we have also focused on monitoring the changes in the contact angles over time following the modification/deposition and aging of the samples. Ti and TiAlV foils, after carbon layer deposition by evaporation (C3) and PLD (C_{PLD}) methods, underwent subsequent laser annealing at an energy of 150 mJ cm^{-2} (L) over 30 days.

Fig. 6 illustrates the change in contact angle: (a) for Ti foil after carbon layer deposition via vapor deposition (Ti/C3) and the PLD method followed by laser annealing (Ti/C_{PLD}/L), compared to the unmodified Ti foil (dashed line), and (b) for TiAlV foil after carbon layer deposition by vapor (TiAlV/C3) and PLD method followed by laser annealing (TiAlV/C_{PLD}/L) compared to unmodified TiAlV foil (dashed line), both monitored for 30 days. The results indicate that Ti and TiAlV foils with carbon layers deposited by the PLD method exhibited smaller changes in contact angle compared to those with the samples with deposited layers. The unmodified Ti foil had a contact angle of $96.3 \pm 0.5^\circ$ (dashed line), while the unmodified TiAlV foil reached a contact angle of $83.1 \pm 1.1^\circ$, (also shown by a dashed line). The Ti/C3 sample recorded an increase in contact angle from the initial $58.6 \pm 2.3^\circ$ to 79.7

Fig. 5. Contact angle on the surface of a titanium foil with a carbon layer deposited by pulsed laser deposition (Ti/C_{PLD}) and subsequent laser annealing (L) with the energy of 150 mJ cm^{-2} in the ambient atmosphere (Ti/C_{PLD}/Latm.) and vacuum (Ti/C_{PLD}/Lvac).

$\pm 2.8^\circ$ by the final measurement day. Conversely, the Ti/C_{PLD}/L sample experienced a slight decrease from the initial $54.4 \pm 2.4^\circ$ to $50.9 \pm 3.2^\circ$, which is nearly constant within the measurement error.

A similar trend was observed for TiAlV foils, although generally with lower contact angle values. The TiAlV/C3 sample showed an initial contact angle of $46.0 \pm 0.8^\circ$, increasing to $79.1 \pm 1.7^\circ$ after 30 days. The TiAlV/C_{PLD}/L sample's contact angle fluctuated from $61.1 \pm 1.0^\circ$ on the first day to $54.9 \pm 3.2^\circ$ by the tenth day, stabilizing at $59.5 \pm 2.5^\circ$ on the final measurement day, indicating a stable state, or aging of the sample.

As we stated before, most cells exhibit optimal adhesion and growth on surfaces with moderate hydrophilicity, typically at contact angles between 40° and 70° . Due to that fact, we have chosen to perform the antibacterial study and cytocompatibility study for samples, which underwent the ageing process (as introduced in **Fig. 6**). Therefore even we still have has the changed morphology and chemistry, the surface of both Ti and TiAlV surface was stabilized from the point of their wettability, resp. surface contact angle. As observed for several papers introduced earlier (for results on polymer, see please (Slepicka et al., 2012), the ageing process may lead to increase of contact angle, and in time stabilization, while the oxygen concentration remains almost similar. Also in our case we expect to occur the same phenomenon, since on the basis of our analysis the increase of oxygen can still be detected, even the contact angle is increasing over time. This could be considered as positive phenomenon, since as stated previously in this manuscript, the contact angle changes induced by ageing process is in „positive range“ for cytocompatibility enhancement, and also the increase in oxygen concentration can be considered as positive, since also reactive species and possible oxygen radical may play an important role in antibacterial properties, as will be discussed also further in the paper.

From these results, it can be concluded that laser exposure (150 mJ cm^{-2}) to the surface of the carbon layer deposited by the PLD method led to stabilization of the contact angle, indicative of sample aging. In contrast, the samples with carbon layers deposited by the C3 method

Fig. 6. Changes in contact angles: (A) Ti foil after deposition with a carbon layer by evaporation (Ti/C3) and PLD method followed by laser annealing with a fluence of 150 mJ cm^{-2} (Ti/C_{PLD/L}) compared to unmodified Ti foil (dashed line) and graph (B) TiAlV foil after depositing a carbon layer by evaporation (TiAlV/C3) and PLD method and subsequent laser annealing with an energy of 150 mJ cm^{-2} (TiAlV/C_{PLD/L}) compared to unmodified TiAlV foil (dashed line), both followed for 30 days.

exhibited changes in contact angle throughout the measurement period, while still increasing in hydrophobicity. Nonetheless, the contact angles of both types of samples remained within the range suitable for evaluating cell adhesion and proliferation at the end of the measurement period.

SEM analysis

We also characterized the surface of both pristine and carbon-deposited (two different methods) Ti and TiAlV foils using SEM. The morphology of the samples (Fig. 7) is consistent with that observed using

the AFM technique. As shown in Fig. 8, the surface chemistry of the pristine TiAlV foil consists of Ti, Al, and V elements. The deposition of carbon using the evaporation technique (C3) resulted in the presence of carbon (5.8 wt. %) and oxygen (3.5 wt. %) on the TiAlV surface.

Surprisingly, the deposition of carbon by PLD led to a significant increase in carbon concentration, reaching up to 63.2 wt.%, which was unexpected. In contrast, the oxygen concentration remained relatively stable (4.0 wt. %). These findings suggest that the biological properties, particularly for the CPLD sample, are likely to be strongly influenced by the carbon-enriched layer.

The surface chemistry of pristine Ti and carbon-deposited Ti foils was

Fig. 7. SEM images of titanium alloy foil (TiAlV pristine) and this substrate after depositing the carbon layer by different methods: "flash" evaporation (C3) and pulsed laser deposition (CPLD). The scanned area was of $30 \times 30 \mu\text{m}^2$ and $10 \times 10 \mu\text{m}^2$.

Fig. 8. EDS spectra of titanium alloy foil (TiAlV_pristine) foil after carbon layer deposition using two different methods: "flash" evaporation (C3) and pulsed laser deposition (CPLD). The scanned area was of $10 \times 10 \mu\text{m}^2$. The element concentrations are in wt. %.

also characterized. As shown in Fig. 9, carbon deposition resulted in increased concentrations of both carbon and oxygen for the carbon-coated Ti foils produced by both PLD and evaporation techniques. For the evaporation method (C3), carbon was detected at 6.3 wt. % along with an equal oxygen concentration (6.4 wt. %) on the Ti surface. In contrast, the carbon concentration on the Ti foils deposited by Ti CPLD was lower, at 2.4 wt. %, while the oxygen concentration increased to 5.6 wt. %. Although a significant rise in both carbon and oxygen levels for evaporated Ti, no corresponding increase in carbon concentration was detected for Ti foil coated with carbon using the PLD technique.

Cytocompatibility

The final step of this study involved assessing the adhesion and proliferation of human osteosarcoma cells (U-2 OS) on titanium and titanium alloy foils. The results were compared to a control, i.e., cells growing on tissue culture polystyrene (TCPS). As previously mentioned, titanium and its alloys are favored for implants due to their excellent biocompatibility, corrosion resistance, and ability to support osseointegration. Surface coatings, particularly DLC layers, are often applied to enhance these properties. These coatings not only increase the material's resistance to wear and corrosion but also improve surface hardness and promote more efficient bone tissue growth, ensuring a stronger and more stable anchoring of the implant. This comprehensive approach

Fig. 9. EDS spectra of titanium foil titanium after depositing the carbon layer by different methods: "flash" evaporation (Ti C3) and pulsed laser deposition (Ti CPLD). The scanned area was $10 \times 10 \mu\text{m}^2$. Concentrations are in wt. %.

contributes to the long-term functionality and reliability of implants in challenging biological environments.

Previous studies (Zareidoost et al., 2012) have demonstrated that surface roughness significantly enhances the adhesion efficiency of osteoblast cells. Increased roughness promotes the formation of integrin clusters facilitating attachment through protein absorption. For materials with surface layers, optimal adhesion of osteoblast cells is achieved at a surface wettability between 75 and 90°. Additionally, surface properties such as roughness and wettability play a crucial role in protein adsorption and conformation. Hydrophobic surfaces significantly affect protein adsorption, which is a key initial phase in the cell interaction with material before cell attachment (Jongwannasiri et al., 2023).

The data in Fig. 10 illustrate the adhesion and proliferation of U-2 OS cells 24, 48, and 72 h after seeding onto Ti and TiAlV foils as well as samples coated with a carbon layer by evaporation (C3) and PLD (CPLD), followed by laser annealing at an energy of 150 mJ cm⁻² (L). These results are compared to the control, i.e. cells grown on TCPS.

The number of U-2 OS cells grown on the evaluated samples after 24 h (green bars in Fig. 10) did not vary from the TCPS control. After 48 h (pink bars in Fig. 10), an increase in cell numbers was noted for almost all samples, except for TiAlV/C3, for which the cell counts slightly declined. Then, after 72 h incubation (blue bars in Fig. 10), the cell number increased again, especially on Ti, Ti/C3, and Ti/CPLD/L samples, on which there was a comparable amount of cells as on TCPS control. The Ti/CPLD/L sample showed an increase in cell numbers compared to the 48 h measurement, but it remained significantly lower than the other Ti samples and exhibited a considerable standard deviation. In the case of the PLD carbon layer, partial peeling of the layer occurred on the surface of the Ti foil, after prolonged exposure to an aqueous environment, which may have contributed to the observed measurement variability.

The highest cell count among the tested samples was detected on the TiAlV sample, surpassing those with a carbon layer but remaining lower than the Ti foil. The TiAlV/C3 sample showed a decrease in cell numbers, while the TiAlV/CPLD/L sample experienced an increase in cell count at both 48 and 72 h compared to the 24-h measurement. However, at 72 h, the cell count was the second lowest among all, including the TCPS control.

The lower number of cells on the TiAlV sample compared to the Ti

Fig. 10. Graph presenting the number of U-2 OS cells after 24, 48, and 72 h from cell seeding on the surface of titanium (Ti) and titanium alloy (TiAlV) foils as well as samples coated with a carbon layer deposited by evaporation (C3) and PLD (CPLD) methods followed by laser annealing with the energy of 150 mJ cm⁻² (L). Cells growing on tissue culture polystyrene (TCPS) served as control.

foil may be attributed to its smoother surface and lower contact angle. The surface morphology of the Ti foil, as depicted in the AFM images in Fig. 3, reveals an organized “scratches” structure that likely enhances cell adhesion. In contrast, the reduced cell numbers observed on the TiAlV samples with a carbon layer may result from decreased surface roughness caused by the deposition process, which could hinder effective cell adhesion and proliferation.

The difference in cell numbers between the TiAlV/C3 and TiAlV/CPLD/L samples may also be related to the characteristics of the carbon layer. As previously mentioned, DLC coatings are known to promote cell adhesion and proliferation, suggesting that the layer containing 61 % of sp³ bonds may exhibit beneficial properties to DLC coatings.

In Fig. 11, there are fluorescence microscopy images of U-2 OS cells after 72 h post-seeding on Ti and TiAlV foils. The samples include those with carbon layers deposited via “flash” evaporation (C3) and PLD (CPLD), followed by laser annealing with an energy of 150 mJ cm⁻² (L). The images show the surfaces of the Ti and TiAlV samples covered with adhered and proliferated cells, which predominantly exhibit a spherical shape and tend to form clusters. This clustering tendency results in a relatively uneven distribution of cells to cluster, as indicated by the considerable variation shown in Fig. 10. A similar phenomenon is observed across other Ti and TiAlV foil samples. Notably, in the Ti/CPLD/L sample, the cells adopt an elongated shape that corresponds to the “scratch” structure of the surface, as depicted in the AFM images in Fig. 3.

On the TiAlV/CPLD/L sample, there was lower cell density compared to the TiAlV sample, with significant cell-free areas present. The cells displayed effective adhesion of filopodia to the substrate. Additional fluorescence microscopy images highlighting cell adhesion and proliferation on the remaining samples and TCPS at 24, 48, and 72 h post-seeding are presented in Figs. 12 and 13. These images offer visual evidence of the morphological changes and dynamics of cell growth over the monitored period.

Antibacterial study

The final step involved analysing the antibacterial properties of the prepared samples against two bacterial strains: Gram-negative (G-) *E. coli* and Gram-positive (G+) *S. aureus*. The number of colony-forming units (CFU) of both bacterial strains (Fig. 14) was determined after 2 and 24 h of contact with the tested samples: Ti and TiAlV foils after the

Fig. 11. Fluorescence microscopy images of human osteosarcoma cells (U-2 OS) 72 h after seeding onto the titanium (Ti) and titanium alloy (TiAlV) foils as well as samples further coated with a carbon layer by vapor deposition (C3) and PLD (CPLD) followed by laser annealing with the energy of 150 mJ cm⁻² (L). The images are on a scale of 300 × 300 μm². Only selected samples are presented, control and other samples are introduced further in Figs. 12 and 13.

Fig. 12. Fluorescence microscopy images of human cells from osteosarcoma (U-2 OS) 24, 48, and 72 h after seeding onto Ti foils as well as samples coated with a carbon layer by "flash" evaporation (C3) and PLD (CPLD) method followed by laser annealing with the energy of 150 mJ cm^{-2} (L). Cells growing on TCPS served as controls. The images are on a scale of $300 \times 300 \mu\text{m}^2$.

deposition of a carbon layer using the "flash" vapor deposition (C3) and pulsed laser deposition (PLD), followed by laser annealing at an energy of 150 mJ cm^{-2} (L) in comparison with control.

In the left part of Fig. 14, it is evident that all samples exhibited an inhibitory antibacterial activity against *E. coli* already after 2 h of incubation compared to the control. After 24 h of incubation, this inhibitory effect remained largely unchanged for most samples, except for the TiAlV sample, which showed a notable increase in the CFU number approaching control levels. This increase in bacterial count may be attributed to the lower contact angle and the smoother surface of TiAlV vs. Ti foil. The roughness and higher contact angle of the carbon-coated Ti foil likely rendered it less conducive to bacteria attachment, as carbon layers are known for their antibacterial properties. Notably, the carbon layer deposited by the PLD method exhibited greater variability than those deposited by the C3 method, possibly due to partial exfoliation of the carbon layer after prolonged exposure to the aqueous environment. The partial exfoliation is however minimal, the major effect is considered as carbon transformation upon laser annealing process. It is evident that for *E. coli* the antibacterial properties are similar for carbon layer prepared by vapor deposition, pulsed laser deposition and those samples subsequently treated by excimer.

Next, the antibacterial effects against *S. aureus*, presented in the right part of Fig. 14, revealed that after 2 h of incubation, all evaluated samples exhibited similar efficacy compared to control. However, after 24 h, the Ti-based samples demonstrated significantly higher antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* than the TiAlV samples. Among these, the Ti/CPLD/L sample exhibited the highest antibacterial efficacy, with CFU values nearing zero. The Ti/C3 sample had the lowest inhibitory effect among the Ti samples, yet it still managed to eliminate approximately 80 % of the bacteria. For the TiAlV samples, the unmodified TiAlV sample

Fig. 13. Images from fluorescence microscopy of human cells from osteosarcoma (U-2 OS) 24, 48, and 72 h after seeding onto TiAlV foils as well as samples coated with a carbon layer using "flash" evaporation (C3) and PLD (CPLD) methods followed by laser annealing with the energy of 150 mJ cm^{-2} (L). Cells growing on TCPS served as controls. The image dimension is $300 \times 300 \mu\text{m}^2$.

demonstrated the least antibacterial effect, consistent with the findings for *E. coli*. In contrast, the carbon-coated TiAlV samples effectively inhibited $>80 \%$ of bacterial growth. The most effective combination is PLD layer combined with subsequent laser annealing. This effectivity is also substrate specific, since the best antibacterial properties were exhibited on Ti sample, while higher CFU numbers were observed on TiAlV sample. It has been proposed that carbon-based nanomaterials cause membrane damage in bacteria due to an oxidative stress. According to recent studies the physical interaction of carbon-based nanomaterials with bacteria, rather than oxidative stress, is the primary antimicrobial activity of these nanostructures (Adolfsson et al., 2019; Xin et al., 2019; Jonathan et al., 2024; Maleki Dizaj, 2015). The similar mechanism could be also suggested for treated samples by excimer laser, probably also specific forms of carbon nanoparticles are produced by the process as described e.g. in (Jonathan et al., 2024; Maleki Dizaj, 2015).

The TiAlV coated with carbon deposited by PLD technique was determined as DLC coating. The DLC layer during excimer laser annealing is enhanced, the carbon layer undergo the transformation. The effect of DLC coating was studied in detail in (Jongwannasiri et al., 2023) on TiAlV substrate, Diamond-like carbon (DLC)-coated titanium surface inhibits bacterial growth and modulates human alveolar bone cell responses in vitro. One of the key parameter, besides the changes in chemistry and morphology is the improved wear resistance of functional diamond like carbon coated Ti-6Al-4V alloys, which was confirmed in (Choudhury et al., 2016). A comprehensive review of the biomedical applications of titanium alloys were discussed in (Marin et al., 2024) in detail. The results of Ti-AlV alloy with carbon (in volume) were discussed in (Szkliniarz et al., 2015), significant changes in hardness and surface stability were observed, while also carbide phase was detected. On the basis of several papers published so far (Ma et al., 2022; Kumar

Fig. 14. Antibacterial activity of titanium (Ti) and titanium alloy (TiAlV) foils as well as samples coated with a carbon layer using vapor deposition (C3) and PLD (CPLD) followed by laser annealing with the energy of 150 mJ cm^{-2} (L). The number of colony-forming units (CFU) of *E. coli* (left graph) and *S. aureus* (right graph) after 2 and 24-hour contact with the tested samples was compared to the control (bacteria incubated only with PBS).

et al., 2024; Lorenzetti et al., 2015) we believe that the major influence on antibacterial properties of carbon of Ti and/or TiAlV surfaces is enhancement of surface mechanical properties in combination with wettability modification, however the formation of specific carbon nanostructure plays also an important role in their antibacterial response.

One of the major phenomenon influencing the bacterial adhesion or growth inhibition is considered electron transfer or reactive oxygen species generation (Juan et al., 2021; Li et al., 2023; Jana et al., 2021), which are often linked to carbon hybridization. Cells produce ROS as a controlled physiological process, but increasing ROS becomes pathological and leads to oxidative stress and disease. The induction of oxidative stress is an imbalance between the production of radical species and the antioxidant defense systems, which can cause damage to cellular biomolecules, including lipids, proteins and DNA (Juan et al., 2021). Reactive oxygen species (ROS) are produced as a normal product of plant cellular metabolism. Various environmental stresses lead to excessive production of ROS causing progressive oxidative damage and ultimately cell death (Sharma et al., 2012). Despite their destructive activity, they are well-described second messengers in a variety of cellular processes, including conferment of tolerance to various environmental stresses. The carbon may play an important role in reactive oxygen species (ROS) formation, the generation of ROS was observed through electron transfer from carboxylated single-walled carbon nanotubes in water (Hsieh et al., 2014; Hsieh et al., 2015).

In this paper, we have observed by Raman spectroscopy that the PLD method produced a higher sp³ carbon bond content than the evaporation method (61 vs. 47 %). This important ratio has a direct impact on the biological properties of studied samples, especially influencing the cytocompatibility. Thin diamond-like carbon (DLC) films of various diamond/graphitic content were created using pulsed laser deposition method. "Diamond" sp³ concentration in region from 32 % to 62 % was determined using X-ray photoelectron and Auger spectroscopy (Jelínek et al., 2010), while sp³, sp² bonds and surface and biological properties of DLC layers were discussed accordingly to our findings. It was confirmed that studied DLC biocompatibility of textile blood vessels by in vivo tests with sheep, the sp³ content varied from 40 % to 60 %. Better results were achieved for higher sp³ content (Kocourek et al., 2008).

Evaluation of the potential of DLC coatings for biomedical applications, with a specific focus on their impact on biocompatibility, corrosion resistance, and wear performance is described in (Shah et al., 2024), the influence of DLC coatings on the biocompatibility of medical devices is described in detail. Current strategies to enhance the corrosion resistance of DLC-coated implants are discussed as well. Tuning C–C sp²/sp³ ratio of DLC films for biomedical application by varying the N₂ flow rate, sp²/sp³ ratio 1.74 was achieved (Rao, 2020).

Conclusions

The "flash" vapor deposition and pulsed laser deposition methods applied carbon to titanium and titanium alloy foils revealed notable differences in cytocompatibility and antimicrobial properties. These effects also vary significantly with the used substrate. The difference can be caused by surface roughness difference. The carbon layer deposited by "flash" vapour on titanium exhibited slight increase of cell proliferation of U-2 OS cells, but on titanium alloy resulted in cell death. The antibacterial effect on *E. coli* and *S. aureus* was decreased for titanium and increased for titanium alloy. In contrast, the PLD-deposited layer only slightly decreased cell proliferation on both substrates, but provided superior antibacterial activity. This suggests the potential of PLD-deposited carbon layers for biomedical applications.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Petr Slepicka: Writing – original draft, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition. **Kludia Hurtuková:** Investigation. **Silvie Rimpelová:** Writing – review & editing, Formal analysis. **Sárka Trhoňová:** Investigation. **Jiří Martan:** Formal analysis, Data curation. **Michal Procházka:** Investigation, Data curation. **Václav Švorčík:** Formal analysis. **Nikola Slepicková Kasálková:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Data curation.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence

the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgments

This work was supported by the Project OP JAK MEBioSys, No CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004634, of the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports, which is co-funded by the European Union. This work was supported by the Czech Science Foundation under project 22-04006S.

Data availability

The data presented in this study are available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14513706>.

References

- Adolfsson, K.H., et al., 2019. Importance of surface functionalities for antibacterial properties of carbon spheres. *Adv. Sustainable Syst.* 2019, 1800148.
- Al-Azzam, N., Alazzam, A., 2022. Micropatterning of cells via adjusting surface wettability using plasma treatment and graphene oxide deposition. *PLoS One* 17 (6), e0269914.
- Alotaibi, S., Manjunatha, K.N., 2018. Stability of hydrogenated amorphous carbon thin films for application in electronic devices. *Diam. Relat. Mater.* 90, 172–180.
- Bewilogua, K., Hofmann, D., 2014. History of diamond-like carbon films — From first experiments to worldwide applications. *Surf. Coat. Technol.* 242, 214–225.
- Bi, F., et al., 2017. Characteristics of amorphous carbon films to resist high potential impact in PEMFCs bipolar plates for automotive application. *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy* 42 (20), 14279–14289.
- Birkett, M., et al., 2023. Multi-functional bioactive silver- and copper-doped diamond-like carbon coatings for medical implants. *Acta Biomater.* 167, 54–68.
- Bociaga, D., et al., 2015. Silver-doped nanocomposite carbon coatings (Ag-DLC) for biomedical applications – physicochemical and biological evaluation. *Appl. Surf. Sci.* 355, 388–397.
- Buchegger, S., et al., 2017. Multilayer diamond-like amorphous carbon coatings produced by ion irradiation of polymer films. *Surf. Coat. Technol.* 327, 42–47.
- Caschera, D., et al., 2011. Effect of composition on mechanical behaviour of diamond-like carbon coatings modified with titanium. *Thin. Solid. Films.* 519 (10), 3061–3067.
- Choudhury, D., et al., 2016. Improved wear resistance of functional diamond like carbon coated Ti–6Al–4V alloys in an edge loading conditions. *J. Mechan. Behavior Biomed. Mater.* 59, 586–595.
- Doll, G.L., 2022. Surface engineering in wind turbine tribology. *Surf. Coat. Technol.* 442, 128545–128545.
- Dorner, A., et al., 2001. Diamond-like carbon-coated Ti6Al4V: influence of the coating thickness on the structure and the abrasive wear resistance. *Wear.* 249 (5–6), 489–497.
- Dwivedi, N., et al., 2011. Nanostructured titanium/diamond-like carbon multilayer films: deposition, characterization, and applications. *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 3 (11), 4268–4278.
- Erdemir, A., Donnet, C., 2006. Tribology of diamond-like carbon films: recent progress and future prospects. *J. Phys. D: Appl. Phys.* 39 (18), R311–R327.
- Gangopadhyay, A., 1998. Mechanical and tribological properties of amorphous carbon films. *Tribol. Lett.* 5 (1), 25–39.
- Grausova, L., et al., 2009. Fullerene C60 films of continuous and micropatterned morphology as substrates for adhesion and growth of bone cells. *Diamond Rel. Mater.* 18, 578.
- Harrasser, N., et al., 2016. Antibacterial potency of different deposition methods of silver and copper containing diamond-like carbon coated polyethylene. *Biomater. Res.* 20 (1).
- Honglerkongsakul, K., et al., 2010. Electrical and optical properties of diamond-like carbon films deposited by pulsed laser ablation. *Diam. Relat. Mater.* 19 (7–9), 999–1002.
- Hsieh, H.S., et al., 2014. Light-Independent reactive oxygen species (ROS) formation through electron transfer from carboxylated single-walled carbon nanotubes in water. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 48, 11330–11336.
- Hsieh, H.S., et al., 2015. Reactive oxygen species generation and dispersant-dependent electron transfer through single-walled carbon nanotubes in water. *Carbon N Y* 89, 361–371.
- Hu, A., et al., 2007. Optical and microstructural properties of diamond-like carbon films grown by pulsed laser deposition. *Diam. Relat. Mater.* 16 (1), 149–154.
- Iwamura, E. (2013). Hybridized carbon nanocomposite thin films: synthesis, structures and tribological properties. In *Tribol. Polym. Nanocompos.*; Elsevier, pp. 405–435.
- Jackson, M.J., et al., 2016. Titanium and titanium alloy applications in medicine. *Surg. Tools Med. Devices.* Springer, pp. 475–517.
- Jana, D., et al., 2021. Hybrid carbon dot assembly as a reactive oxygen species nanogenerator for ultrasound-assisted tumor ablation. *JACS.* Au 1, 2328–2338.
- Jastrzębski, K., et al., 2021. Induced biological response in contact with Ag- and Cu-doped carbon coatings for potential orthopedic applications. *Mater* 14 (8), 1861–1861.
- Jelínek, M., et al., 2010. Biocompatibility and sp²/sp³ ratio of laser created DLC films. *Mater. Sci. Eng. B* 169, 89–93.
- Jing, P.P., et al., 2021. Influence of Ag doping on the microstructure, mechanical properties, and adhesion stability of diamond-like carbon films. *Surf. Coat. Technol.* 405, 126542–126542.
- Jonathan, F., et al., 2024. Characteristics and antibacterial properties of carbon nanoparticles synthesized by the pulsed laser ablation method in various liquid media. *Environment. Nanotechnol. Monitor. Manag.* 21, 100909.
- Jongwanasiri, C., et al., 2023a. Diamond-like carbon (DLC)-coated titanium surface inhibits bacterial growth and modulates human alveolar bone cell responses in vitro. *Diam. Relat. Mater.* 136, 110022–110022.
- Jongwanasiri, Ch., et al., 2023b. Diamond-like carbon (DLC)-coated titanium surface inhibits bacterial growth and modulates human alveolar bone cell responses in vitro. *Diamond Rel. Mater.* 136, 110022.
- Juan, C.A., et al., 2021. The chemistry of reactive oxygen species (ROS) revisited: outlining their role in biological macromolecules (DNA, lipids and proteins) and induced pathologies. *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* 28, 4642.
- Karkalos, N.E., et al., 2023. A statistical and optimization study on the influence of different abrasive types on kerf quality and productivity during abrasive waterjet (AWJ) milling of Ti-4Al-6V. *Mater* 17 (1), 11–11.
- Kattamis, T.Z., et al., 1996. Deposition and mechanical property evaluation of amorphous silicon-containing diamond-like carbon (Si-DLC) coatings on steel. *J. Adhes. Sci. Technol.* 10 (10), 939–949.
- Kocurek, T., et al., 2008. DLC coating of textile blood vessels using PLD. *Appl. Phys. A* 93, 627–632.
- Kopova, I., et al., 2018. Growth of primary human osteoblasts on plasma-treated and nanodiamond-coated PTFE polymer foils. *Phys. Status Solidi B*, 1700595.
- Kumar, A., et al., 2024. Surface modification of Ti6Al4V alloy via advanced coatings: mechanical, tribological, corrosion, wetting, and biocompatibility studies. *J. Alloys Compounds* 989, 174418.
- Li, Q., et al., 2023. Carbon quantum dots as ROS-generator and -scavenger: a comprehensive review. *Dyes and Pigments* 208, 110784.
- Lin, J., et al., 2017. Thick diamond-like carbon coatings deposited by deep oscillation magnetron sputtering. *Surf. Coat. Technol.* 315, 294–302.
- Lišková, J., et al., 2019. Heat-treated carbon coatings on poly (L-lactide) foils for tissue engineering. *Mater. Sci. Eng. C* 100, 117–128.
- Lorenzetti, M., et al., 2015. The Influence of surface modification on bacterial adhesion to titanium-based substrates. *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 7, 1644–1651.
- Ma, T., et al., 2022. The antibacterial activity comparison between novel carbon-based nanofilm coated titanium alloy and Co-Cr-Mo alloy. *E. Based Complement. Alternative Med.* Article ID 5463383.
- Majhy, B., et al., 2021. Effect of surface energy and roughness on cell adhesion and growth – Facile surface modification for enhanced cell culture. *RSC. Adv.* 11 (25), 15467–15476.
- Maleki Dizaj, S., 2015. Antimicrobial activity of carbon-based nanoparticles. *Adv. Pharm. Bull.* 5, 19–23.
- Marciano, F.R., et al., 2009a. Diamond-like carbon films produced from high deposition rates exhibit antibacterial activity. *Synth. Met.* 159 (21–22), 2167–2169.
- Marciano, F.R., et al., 2009b. Antibacterial activity of DLC and Ag–DLC films produced by PECVD technique. *Diam. Relat. Mater.* 18 (5–8), 1010–1014.
- Marciano, F.R., et al., 2011. Investigation into the antibacterial property and bacterial adhesion of diamond-like carbon films. *Vacuum.* 85 (6), 662–666.
- Marin, E., et al., 2024. Biomedical applications of titanium alloys: a comprehensive review. *Materials (Basel)* 17, 114.
- Mutreja, L., et al., 2020. Cell responses to titanium and titanium alloys. *Handb. Biomater. Biocompat.* Elsevier, pp. 423–452.
- Neděla, O., et al., 2017. Surface modification of polymer substrates for biomedical applications. *Materials (Basel)* 10, 1115–1136.
- Ohtake, N., et al., 2021. Properties and classification of diamond-like carbon films. *Mater* 14 (2), 315.
- Orrit-Prat, J., et al., 2021. Bactericidal silver-doped DLC coatings obtained by pulsed filtered cathodic arc co-deposition. *Surf. Coat. Technol.* 411, 126977.
- Paul, R., et al., 2009. Surface plasmon characteristics of nanocrystalline gold/DLC composite films prepared by plasma CVD technique. *Mater. Sci. Eng. B* 164 (3), 156–164.
- Rajak, D.K., et al., 2021. Diamond-like carbon (DLC) coatings: classification, properties, and applications. *Appl. Sci.* 11 (10), 4445.
- Rao, X., 2020. Tuning C–C sp²/sp³ ratio of DLC films in FCVA system for biomedical application. *Bioact. Mater.* 5, 192–200.
- Ray, S.C., et al., 2016. Iron, nitrogen and silicon doped diamond-like carbon (DLC) thin films: a comparative study. *Thin. Solid. Films.* 610, 42–47.
- Ren, Z., et al., 2019. A boron-doped diamond-like carbon coating with high hardness and low friction coefficient. *Wear.* 436–437, 203031.
- Robertson, J., 2002. Diamond-like amorphous carbon. *Mater. Sci. Eng. R Rep.* 37 (4–6), 129–281.
- Sarraf, M., et al., 2021. A state-of-the-art review of the fabrication and characteristics of titanium and its alloys for biomedical applications. *Bio-Des. Manuf.* 5, 1–25.
- Sasamoto, T., et al., 2021. Antibacterial fluorinated diamond-like carbon coating promotes osteogenesis—Comparison with titanium alloy. *Appl. Sci.* 11 (20), 9451–9451.
- Shah, R., et al., 2024. DLC coatings in biomedical applications – review on current advantages, existing challenges, and future directions. *Surf. Coat. Technol.* 487, 131006.
- Sharifahmadian, O., et al., 2023. Doping effects on the tribological performance of diamond-like carbon coatings: a review. *J. Mater. Res. Technol.* 27, 7748–7765.
- Sharma, P., et al., 2012. Reactive oxygen species, oxidative damage, and antioxidative defense mechanism in plants under stressful conditions. *J. Botany* 2012, Article ID 217037.

- Slepicka, P., et al., 2012. Nanostructuring of polymethylpentene by plasma and heat treatment for improved biocompatibility. *Polym. Deg. Stab.* 97, 1075–1082.
- Slepicka, P., et al., 2015. Nano-structured and functionalized surfaces for cytocompatibility improvement and bactericidal action. *Biotechnol. Advances* 33, 1120–1129.
- Slepicka, P., et al., 2018. Polymer nanostructures for bioapplications induced by laser treatment. *Biotechnol. Adv.* 36, 839–855.
- Slepicka, P., et al., 2018. Plasma induced cytocompatibility of stabilized poly-L-lactic acid doped with graphene nanoplatelets. *Reactive Funct. Polym.* 131, 266–275.
- Slepická, P., et al., 2015. Uhlíkové nanovrstvy deponované na laserem modifikovaný film z kyseliny poly(L-mléčné). *Chem. Listy* 109, 879–884.
- Švorčík, V., et al., 2009. Characterization of carbon nanolayers flash evaporated on PET and PTFE. *Carbon N Y* 47 (7), 1770–1778.
- Švorčík, V., et al., 2024. Cytocompatibility of polymers grafted by activated carbon nanoparticles. *Carbon N Y* 69, 361–371.
- Szkliniarz, A., et al., 2015. Thermal stability of Ti-6Al-4V alloy with carbon content. *Solid State Phenomena* 226, 23–28.
- Țălu, Ș., et al., 2020. Multifractal investigation of Ag/DLC nanocomposite thin films. *Sci. Rep.* 10 (1).
- Vetter, J., 2014. 60 years of DLC coatings: historical highlights and technical review of cathodic arc processes to synthesize various DLC types, and their evolution for industrial applications. *Surf. Coat. Technol.* 257, 213–240.
- Viteri, V.S.de, Fuentes, E., 2013. Titanium and titanium alloys as biomaterials. *Tribol. - Fundam. Adv.*
- Voevodin, A.A., et al., 1999. Nanocomposite tribological coatings for aerospace applications. *Surf. Coat. Technol.* 116-119, 36–45.
- Wang, H., et al., 2021. Structure characterization and antibacterial properties of Ag-DLC films fabricated by dual-targets HiPIMS. *Surf. Coat. Technol.* 410, 126967.
- Xin, Q., et al., 2019. Antibacterial carbon-based nanomaterials. *Adv. Mater.* 31, 1804838.
- Žáková, P., et al., 2016. Cytocompatibility of amine functionalized carbon nanoparticles grafted on polyethylene. *Mater. Sci. Eng. C* 60, 394–401.
- Žáková, P., et al., 2017. Cytocompatibility of polyethylene grafted with triethylenetetramine functionalized carbon nanoparticles. *Appl. Surf. Sci.* 422, 809–816.
- Zareidoost, A., et al., 2012. The relationship of surface roughness and cell response of chemical surface modification of titanium. *J. Mater. Sci.: Mater. Med.* 23 (6), 1479–1488.
- Zhang, M., et al., 2020. Mechanical properties and biocompatibility of Ti-doped diamond-like carbon films. *ACS. Omega* 5 (36), 22772–22777.
- Zia, A.W., 2020. New generation carbon particles embedded diamond-like carbon coatings for transportation industry. *Adv. Smart Coat. Thin Films Future Ind. Biomed. Eng. Appl. Elsevier*, pp. 307–332.
- Zia, A.W., et al., 2023. Soft diamond-like carbon coatings with superior biocompatibility for medical applications. *Ceram. Int.* 49 (11), 17203–17211.